

Chemical composition of leaf essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit

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Abstract : Essential oil of leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit collected from Kumaon region of Uttarakhand state of India was obtained by steam distillation using clevenger apparatus. The oil were analyzed by GC and GC-MS. 27 Compounds constituting 87.70% of total oil have been identified, the major ones being 1,8-cineole (17.61%), *E*-caryophyllene (15.23%), sabinene (9.42%), terpinolene (8.87%) and bicyclogermacrene (5.52%).

Keywords : *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit, essential oil, 1,8-cineole, *E*-caryophyllene, sabinene, terpinolene, bicyclogermacrene.

Introduction

Hyptis suaveolens (L.) Poit is used plant as stimulant, sudorific, carminative, galactogogue, antispasmodic, anti rheumatic and as a cure for parasitic cutaneous diseases²⁻⁴. Plant leaves are reported to have anticancer properties, relieves stomach ache and fever². Plant is also reported useful in infection of uterus, and as snuff to stop bleeding of the nose¹. Medicinal plants belonging to the family Lamiaceae were chemically screened for their chemical constituents including alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids and phenols⁵. The allelochemicals present in leaf residues of *Hyptis suaveolens* may be used as potential bio herbicide to control *Parthenium hysterophorus*⁶. Its phytoconstituents may also be responsible for antimicrobial activity⁷. Antioxidant and antimicrobial activity was reported in methanolic root extracts of *Hyptis suaveolens*⁸. Essential oil of *H. suaveolens* showed repellent activity against *S. granaries*, along with sabinene, terpinoline and β -caryophyllene as major compounds of oil⁹. Monoterpenes (1,8-cineole, sabinene, terpinolene as major components) were reported in leaf essential oil *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit¹⁰. Flavonoids were reported in the leaves of *H. suaveolens*¹¹. Tonzibo *et al.* investigated that the constituents of essential oil extracted from aerial part of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) collected in different locations on Côte d'Ivoire were obtained by hydro distillation and analyzed by GC and GC/MS¹².

Hyptis suaveolens (L.) plant belongs to the family

Lamiaceae, is commonly known as wilayati tusi^{13,14}. Plant is native to Tropical America and is now spread all over world, especially in the tropical areas¹³. American Mint is a terrestrial, annual, erect, aromatic herb, up to 200 cm tall. Soil characteristics and nutrient supply are of great importance for growth and development of many plant species.

Material and methods :

The plant materials and identification :

Leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) were collected during its flowering period from Haldwani (29°13'21 N, 79°31'42 E) in Kumaun Region of Uttarakhand, India. The botanical identification of the specimen was done at the Botany Department, Kumaon University, Nainital, and submitted sample at Botanical Survey of India, North Regional Centre, Dehradun (India) for future reference (Acc. No. 114009).

Isolation of essential oil :

The leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* were hydro distilled separately for 3 h using a Clevenger apparatus. The essential oil obtained was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and stored at 4 °C until analysis. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed by distillation using a thin film rotary vacuum evaporator at 25–30 °C. The oil yield was 0.1% (v/w).

Gas chromatographic analysis :

The oil was analyzed by using a Shimadzu 2010 auto

Table. Chemical composition of leaf essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit

Peak No.	Retention time	Compounds identified	%	RI value	KI value
1.	3.020	α -Thujene	1.03	921	930
2.	3.144	α -Pinene	4.77	929	939
3.	3.373	Camphene	0.17	944	954
4.	3.727	Sabinene	9.42	967	975
5.	3.945	Myrcene	0.69	982	990
6.	4.267	α -Phellandrine	2.45	1002	1002
7.	4.386	δ -3-Carene	0.39	1007	1011
8.	4.501	α -Terpinene	1.48	1012	1017
9.	4.668	<i>p</i> -Cymene	2.99	1018	1024
10.	4.843	1,8-Cineole	7.61	1026	1031
11.	5.429	γ -Terpinene	2.83	1050	1059
12.	5.643	<i>cis</i> -Sabinene hydrate	0.06	1059	1070
13.	6.203	Terpinolene	8.87	1082	1088
14.	6.915	Fenchyl alcohol	1.51	1109	1116
15.	8.880	Terpinen-4-ol	1.70	1170	1177
16.	14.653	δ -Elemene	0.18	1329	1338
17.	16.158	α -Copaene	0.99	1367	1376
18.	16.800	β -Elemene	0.671	1384	1390
19.	17.912	E-Caryophyllene	5.23	1398	1408
20.	18.500	<i>trans</i> - α -Bergamotene	2.67	1427	1434
21.	19.166	α -Humulene	1.04	1444	1454
22.	20.242	Germacrene D	0.86	1472	1479
23.	20.438	β -Salinene	0.86	1477	1490
24.	20.876	β -Cyclogermacrene	5.52	1488	1500
25.	23.946	Spathulenol	0.40	1569	1578
26.	26.795	Intermedol	0.40	1646	1665
27.	40.111	Abietatriene	1.23	2043	2056
28.	40.850	Abietadiene	1.15	2067	2087
29.	44.035	Retinol	0.53	2174	2188

system GC. The column temperature was programmed at 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and than 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 15 min, using N₂/air at 30.0 mL/min column head pressure as carrier gas, the injector temperature was 270 °C and detector (FID, Flame ionization detector) temperature 280 °C.

Gas chromatographic-mass spectrometric analysis (GC-MS) :

The GC-MS used was Autosystem 2010 GC (Rtx-5, 30 m×0.25 mm, i.d. FID 0.25 μ m) coupled with Shimadzu QP 2010 plus with thermal desorption system TD 20 with (Rtx-5) fused silica capillary column (30 m×0.25 mm with film thickness 0.25 μ m). The column

temperature was 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and then 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 21 min, using helium as carrier gas. The injector temperature was 230 °C and 0.2 μ L in *n*-hexane; with split ratio of 1 : 30 MS were taken at 70 eV with a mass range of 40–650 amu.

Identification of the compounds :

Identification of constituents was done on the basis of MS Library search (NIST : NIH version 2.1 and Wiley, 7th edition), by comparing with the MS literature data, their RI and KI values¹⁵. The relative amounts of individual components were calculated based on GC peak area (FID response) without using correction factor.

Results and discussion

The essential oil composition of leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) of family Lamiaceae was collected during its flowering period from Haldwani (altitude approx. 1420 ft.). GC and GC/MS analyzed chemical composition of essential oil and identification of constituents was done on the basis of MS Library search by comparing with the MS literature data, their RI and KI values. The oil yield was obtained 0.1% (v/w). The chemical composition of the essential oil studied is presented in the Table. 27 Compounds constituting 87.70% of total oil have been identified. The samples collected from Bhabhar region were predominantly dominated by 65.55% hydrocarbons (35.15% monoterpenes and 30.40% sesquiterpenes) while only 22.15% are their oxygenated derivatives. It appears that this plant variety belongs to a chemotype having lesser sabinene (9.42%) and more of 1,8-cineole (17.61%), and *E*-caryophyllene (15.23%).

Other compounds represented in essential oils analysis showed that the essential oil of leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) constitutes terpinolene (8.87%), bicyclogermacrene (5.52%), α -pinene (4.77%), β -cymene (2.99%), γ -terpinene (2.83%), *trans*- α -bergomotene (2.67%), α -phellandrene (2.45%), terpinen-4-ol (1.70%), fenchyl alcohol (1.51%), α -terpinene (1.48%), abietatriene (1.23%), α -humulene (1.04%) and α -thujene (1.03%) as main constituents. Compounds constituting 12.30% of total oil are unidentified. Presence of oxygenated compounds in oil indicates that oil may show good bioactivity. To the best of our knowledge, no work has been done on the chemical variability of essential oil of *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit growing wild in Kumaon region of Uttarakhand. This is the first report on chemical composition of essential oil of *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit growing in Haldwani (Kumaon Region), Uttarakhand, India.

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